

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4400

p-ISSN 3082-5733

VOLUME I ISSUE VI

ACADEMIC FRONTIERS

A Multidisciplinary E-Publication

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
INTERNATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
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Butuan City, Philippines
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Academic Frontiers
A Multidisciplinary e-Publication
Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4400 ISSN (Print) 3082-5733
Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
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Pages 74-84

Professional Impact and Satisfaction of Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc.

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Date received: October 20, 2025

Date revised: October 21, 2025

Date accepted: October 31, 2025

Originality: 91%

Grammarly Score: 100%

Similarity: 7%

Recommended citation:

Alvarez, B. A., & Diaz, R. R. (2025). Professional Impact and Satisfaction of Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. *ACADEMIC FRONTIERS Multidisciplinary e-Publication*, 1(6), 74-84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17500588>

Abstract.

Graduate education plays a pivotal role in enhancing educators' competencies by equipping them with advanced pedagogical, managerial, and research skills vital for professional growth. This study assessed the professional impact and satisfaction levels of Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. for the school years 2019-2024. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, 250 MAEd graduates were surveyed using an adapted and validated questionnaire. Results revealed that most respondents were mid-career, female educators, specializing primarily in Educational Management and affiliated with public institutions. They held mid-level to senior positions and possessed significant teaching experience. Graduates demonstrated high proficiency in leadership, management, communication, social, and research skills—indicating the program's effectiveness in producing competent educational leaders. Similarly, they reported a high level of satisfaction with faculty competence, instructional quality, institutional support, and available learning resources. Statistical analyses using non-parametric tests revealed no significant differences in professional impact or satisfaction when grouped by demographic profile, but a strong positive correlation existed between professional impact and satisfaction. These findings highlight that effective MAEd preparation fosters both enhanced competencies and greater career satisfaction. Consequently, a strategic enhancement program was proposed, emphasizing continuous faculty development, curriculum refinement, resource improvement, and professional growth initiatives to ensure sustained educational excellence.

Keywords: MAEd Program Impact, Graduate Satisfaction, Leadership and Management, Research Skills, Educational Advancement

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1.0 Introduction

In the evolving landscape of education, advanced degrees such as the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) are indispensable for promoting professional competence, leadership, and personal fulfillment among educators. Graduate programs strengthen teaching, management, and research capacities – skills crucial for addressing 21st-century learning challenges. According to Buenvenida and Yazon (2017), MAEd graduates attribute their professional growth to the diverse competencies acquired through graduate education. Cruz (2024) further emphasized that graduate programs cultivate innovation and adaptability among teachers, aligning educational practice with modern learning environments. Likewise, Tadeo and Bueno (2024) asserted that comprehensive MAEd curricula provide the theoretical and practical foundation necessary for educators' career advancement.

Internationally, the integration of theory and practice is recognized as a defining characteristic of successful graduate education. Dumlao et al. (2024) and Cruz and Velasco (2023) highlighted that case-based teaching, experiential learning, and the use of technology-driven strategies foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and innovation among graduates. Marquez et al. (2022) supported this by noting that collaborative and technology-enhanced programs produce professionals who can adapt to the changing educational landscape.

In the Philippines, reforms in higher education aim to elevate teaching standards and strengthen research culture (David et al., 2020). Aguilar et al. (2021) noted that institutional resources and faculty expertise directly affect graduate satisfaction and professional performance. This underscores the importance of maintaining quality instruction and relevant curricula in producing competent educators. Pursuing a master's degree not only enhances qualifications but also fosters career mobility and personal growth (Aguilar et al., 2023). Graduate students often express satisfaction when their academic experiences translate into improved leadership, teaching, and research capacities.

At Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. (CKC), the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) program – administered through the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR) – was designed to develop leadership, instructional expertise, and research productivity in alignment with CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 15, s. 2019. Despite numerous graduate programs offered nationwide, limited studies have specifically assessed their impact on graduates' professional development and satisfaction in provincial contexts. This study addressed this gap by evaluating the professional impact and satisfaction levels of CKC MAEd graduates from 2019 to 2024, focusing on how the program enhanced their competencies and overall fulfillment.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, which is suitable for determining relationships among naturally occurring variables without manipulation. As defined by Creswell (2014), this design effectively describes participant characteristics and examines correlations among variables such as demographic profiles, skill development, and satisfaction. The descriptive phase outlined the graduates' demographic profile, while the correlational component examined the association between professional impact and satisfaction.

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2.2 Research Locale

The study was conducted at Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. (CKC), a Franciscan-Catholic institution founded in 1905. Located in Calbayog City, Samar, CKC is one of Eastern Visayas' oldest higher education institutions, managed by the Franciscan Friars of the Custody of St. Anthony of Padua. The Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR) offers MAEd programs with specializations in English, Educational Management, Filipino, Mathematics, and Science Education. CKC's commitment to moral formation, research, and educational excellence makes it an ideal site for evaluating graduate outcomes.

2.3 Research Participants

The respondents consisted of 250 MAEd graduates from school years 2019–2024, drawn from a total population of 714 graduates. The sample size was determined using the Raosoft online calculator with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Table 1 illustrates that the largest number of respondents (34%) were from academic year 2021–2022. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure proportional representation from each academic year and to minimize sampling bias.

2.4 Research Instrument

The study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire from Buenvinida and Yazon (2017), divided into three parts:

Part I: Demographic profile (age, gender, specialization, agency affiliation, rank, service length, and year graduated).

Part II: Extent of professional impact across five domains—leadership, management, social, communication, and research skills—rated on a 5-point Likert scale.

Part III: Satisfaction level concerning faculty competence, instructional quality, learning resources, support services, and student development, also measured on a 5-point Likert scale.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

Formal permission was obtained from the CKC administration and research adviser. The validated questionnaires were distributed via in-person, email, and Google Forms, accommodating respondents' accessibility. Clear instructions and follow-up reminders were provided to maximize response rates. Completed responses were collected, tabulated, and analyzed using non-parametric statistical tests at a 0.05 significance level.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

This research strictly adhered to the ethical standards governing educational research as mandated by the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR) of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the College Research Ethics Committee, and permission was secured from the program head to access the list of MAEd graduates. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and each respondent provided informed consent after being fully briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, potential benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by assigning coded identifiers in place of names, and responses were used solely for academic purposes. All data were securely stored in password-protected digital files accessible only to the researchers. In compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173), the study ensured that all personal and sensitive information was collected, processed, and stored responsibly to safeguard participants' privacy and data integrity.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of MAEd Graduates

Profile Variable	Highest Category	%	Interpretation
Age	31-40 years	48.4%	Mostly mid-career professionals
Gender	Female	53.6%	Female-dominated field
Specialization	Educational Management	73.6%	Focus on leadership and management
Agency	Public Institution	96.4%	Primarily in public service
Position/Rank	Mid-level	38.0%	Advancing educators
Length of Service	6-10 years	56.8%	Experienced teaching professionals
Year Graduated	2021	34.0%	Recent program completers

Table 1. shows the overall result, most MAEd graduates are female, mid-career educators specializing in Educational Management and employed in public institutions. They primarily hold mid-level positions with 6-10 years of service, indicating strong professional experience and a commitment to advancement. The data suggest that the MAEd program effectively develops leadership capacity and promotes professional growth among educators.

Table 2. The Extent of the Professional Impact of Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) Graduates from Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc.

Dimensions	M	SD	Interpretation
Leadership Skills	4.62	.47	Very High
Management Skills	4.58	.46	Very High
Social Skills	4.60	.47	Very High
Communication Skills	4.58	.51	Very High
Research Skills	4.56	.52	Very High
Overall	4.59	.43	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = No Impact At All; 1.81-2.60 = Low; 2.61-3.40 = Moderate; 3.41-4.20 = High; 4.21-5.00 = Very High

Table 2. shows that MAEd graduates demonstrated a *Very High* level of professional impact (M = 4.59, SD = 0.43). Leadership Skills received the highest rating (M = 4.62), highlighting the program's strength in developing decision-making and leadership competencies. Social, Management, and Communication Skills also rated *Very High*, reflecting graduates' strong interpersonal, organizational, and communication abilities. Although Research Skills obtained the lowest mean (M = 4.56), it remains within the *Very High* category, indicating the program's success in fostering scholarly and evidence-

based practices. Overall, the findings affirm the MAEd program’s effectiveness in cultivating well-rounded, competent, and professionally impactful educational leaders.

Table 3. Summary Table on the Level of Satisfaction of MAEd Graduates Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc.

Dimensions	M	SD	Interpretation
Faculty Competence	4.63	0.45	Very Satisfied
Quality of Instruction	4.64	0.44	Very Satisfied
Learning Resources	4.49	0.55	Very Satisfied
Support Services	4.55	0.53	Very Satisfied
Student Development Activities	4.39	0.59	Very Satisfied
Overall	4.54	0.45	Very Satisfied

Legend: 1.00–1.80 = Not Satisfied; 1.81–2.60 = Slightly Satisfied; 2.61–3.40 = Moderately Satisfied; 3.41–4.20 = Satisfied; 4.21–5.00 = Very Satisfied

Table 3 reveal the findings that MAEd graduates from Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. are very satisfied across all evaluated dimensions. The highest satisfaction was noted in Quality of Instruction (M = 4.64, SD = 0.44), reflecting the program’s strength in delivering relevant, updated, and engaging pedagogies. Faculty Competence (M = 4.63, SD = 0.45) also earned high ratings, emphasizing the educators’ expertise and professionalism. Positive feedback was likewise observed for Support Services (M = 4.55, SD = 0.53) and Learning Resources (M = 4.49, SD = 0.55), although the latter suggests opportunities for improvement in resource availability and accessibility. Meanwhile, Student Development Activities (M = 4.39, SD = 0.59) obtained the lowest yet still very satisfied rating, indicating the need to further enhance co-curricular and professional growth initiatives. Overall, the mean score of 4.54 (SD = 0.45) signifies that graduates are highly satisfied, affirming the institution’s commitment to providing quality instruction and comprehensive academic support.

Table 4. Kruskal-Wallis Test of Difference in the Extent of the Professional Impact of MAEd Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. When Grouped According to Their Age

Dimension	Age	N	Mean Rank	H-test	df	p-value	Interpretation
Leadership Skills	<31	82	118.41	1.55ns	2	0.46	Not Significant
Management Skills	<31	82	123.32	1.03ns	2	0.60	Not Significant
Social Skills	<31	82	122.43	1.82ns	2	0.40	Not Significant
Communication Skills	<31	82	120.62	1.08ns	2	0.58	Not Significant
Research Skills	<31	82	124.32	1.34ns	2	0.51	Not Significant
Overall	<31	82	120.97	1.15ns	2	0.56	Not Significant

Level of significance at 0.05; ns – not significant; * – significant; ** – highly significant

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis Test in table 4 show no significant differences in the extent of the professional impact of MAEd graduates when grouped according to age, as all computed p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that graduates, regardless of age, share similar perceptions of how the MAEd program has contributed to their professional growth. The findings suggest that the program’s curriculum, instruction, and academic support are consistently effective across different age groups, promoting equitable opportunities for development.

Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted, confirming that age does not significantly influence the professional impact experienced by graduates.

Table 5. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Difference in the Extent of the Professional Impact of MAEd Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. When Grouped According to Their Profile*

Grouping Variable	Significant Dimension(s)	p-value	Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Age	None	0.40–0.60	No significant difference; consistent professional impact across age groups.	Accepted
Gender	None	0.09–0.76	No significant difference; program impact consistent across all genders.	Accepted
Specialization	None	0.11–0.58	No significant difference; equal impact across specializations.	Accepted
Agency Affiliation	None	0.50–0.81	No significant difference; program effective across work settings.	Accepted
Length of Service	Leadership Skills	0.05	Significant only for leadership; longer service enhances leadership perception.	Rejected for Leadership Skills; Accepted for others
Position/Rank	None	0.30–0.92	No significant difference; consistent impact across job ranks.	Accepted
Year Graduated	None	0.29–0.52	No significant difference; program effectiveness consistent over the years.	Accepted

*Level of significance at 0.05; ns-not significant; *significant; **highly significant*

Table 5 presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis Test on the extent of the professional impact of MAEd graduates from Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. when grouped according to their profile variables. The findings reveal no significant differences across most variables, indicating a consistent perception of the program's impact among graduates.

When grouped according to age, all p-values (Leadership = 0.46, Management = 0.60, Social = 0.40, Communication = 0.58, Research = 0.51, Overall = 0.56) exceed the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that the program's impact is experienced uniformly across different age groups, fostering professional growth without age-related disparities. Similarly, when grouped by gender, all p-values are above 0.05, confirming that the program promotes inclusivity and equitable development of competencies across male, female, LGBTQIA+, and undisclosed respondents.

Grouping by specialization taken also shows no significant differences, as all p-values are greater than 0.05. This finding indicates that the MAEd program delivers consistent professional preparation across various disciplines, including Educational Management, English, Filipino, Mathematics, and Science. Likewise, when grouped by agency affiliation, all p-values exceed 0.05, demonstrating that the program's positive impact extends uniformly to graduates from public, private, and unemployed sectors.

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However, a notable result emerges under length of service, where Leadership Skills reached the 0.05 level of significance, suggesting that graduates with longer service – particularly those with 11–15 years of experience – perceive a stronger leadership impact. Other skill dimensions, however, remain statistically non-significant. Furthermore, when grouped according to present position or rank, all p-values are above 0.05, implying that graduates from varying career levels share similar perceptions of the program’s impact.

Lastly, when grouped by year graduated (2019–2024), all p-values surpass the 0.05 threshold, indicating stable and consistent perceptions across cohorts. Overall, the results suggest that the MAEd program maintains a high level of effectiveness, inclusivity, and sustained professional impact over time, regardless of graduates’ demographic and professional backgrounds.

Table 6. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Difference in the Level of Satisfaction of MAEd Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. Grouped According to their Profile*

Grouping Variable	Result Summary	Decision on Ho ₂	Interpretation Summary
Age	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Satisfaction is consistent across age groups; no age-related differences.
Gender	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Equal satisfaction levels among all gender identities; program is inclusive.
Specialization Taken	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Uniform satisfaction across all specializations; program supports diverse fields.
Agency Affiliation	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Satisfaction is stable across public, private, and unemployed sectors.
Length of Service	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Program satisfaction is consistent regardless of years of service.
Present Position/Rank	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Satisfaction levels do not differ by position; program effective at all ranks.
Year Graduated	All p-values > 0.05	Accepted	Consistent satisfaction across cohorts (2019–2024); stable program quality.

*Level of significance at 0.05; ns-not significant; *significant; **highly significant*

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis Test in Table 6 reveal that there are no significant differences in the level of satisfaction of MAEd graduates from Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. when grouped according to their profile variables, as all p-values exceed the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that the program’s impact on graduates’ satisfaction is uniformly perceived across demographic and professional categories.

When grouped according to age, results ($p > 0.05$) show consistent satisfaction in all dimensions – faculty competence, quality of instruction, learning resources, support services, and student development activities – implying that the program effectively addresses the learning needs of all age groups. This supports Knowles’ (1980) andragogical theory, which posits that adult learners, regardless of age, value relevant and goal-oriented learning experiences.

Similarly, when grouped by gender, specialization, and agency affiliation, all p-values ($p > 0.05$) indicate no significant differences, suggesting that the MAEd program provides equitable and inclusive learning experiences across gender identities, disciplines, and employment sectors. These

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findings align with Suh and Kim (2022), who emphasized that inclusive and well-structured graduate programs yield comparable satisfaction among diverse learners.

Grouping by length of service and present position or rank also showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the program supports professional growth consistently across experience levels and career hierarchies. This finding is consistent with Guskey’s (2002) view that professional satisfaction stems from quality learning experiences rather than years of service.

Finally, when grouped by year graduated (2019–2024), satisfaction remained consistent ($p > 0.05$), highlighting the program’s sustained quality and stable delivery over time (Harvey & Green, 1993). Overall, the findings confirm that the MAEd program maintains a high and consistent level of satisfaction among graduates, regardless of age, gender, specialization, affiliation, experience, position, or graduation year. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted across all variables, reflecting the program’s enduring inclusivity, effectiveness, and academic excellence.

Table 7. Spearman’s Rho Correlation Between the Extent of the Professional Impact and Level of Satisfaction of MAEd Graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc.

Extent of Professional Impact	Faculty Competence	Quality of Instruction	Learning Resources	Support Services	Student Development Activities	Level of Satisfaction
Leadership Skills	.575**	.610**	.596**	.706**	.552**	.672**
Management Skills	.595**	.671**	.663**	.716**	.622**	.724**
Social Skills	.683**	.757**	.733**	.750**	.602**	.772**
Communication Skills	.619**	.686**	.626**	.689**	.636**	.725**
Research Skills	.672**	.632**	.651**	.664**	.548**	.695**
Overall	.701	.742	.749	.785	.674	.817

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 6 presents the results of the Spearman’s Rho correlation analysis, which revealed a strong and positive relationship between the extent of professional impact and the level of satisfaction among MAEd graduates of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. The correlation coefficients (r) ranged from .548 to .817, all statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). These results indicate that as graduates perceive higher professional impact, their satisfaction with the program correspondingly increases, highlighting the program’s overall effectiveness in cultivating professional competence and academic fulfillment.

Among the individual domains, Social Skills ($r = .772$), Management Skills ($r = .724$), and Communication Skills ($r = .725$) demonstrated the highest correlations with overall satisfaction, underscoring the importance of interpersonal, leadership, and communicative competencies in shaping positive graduate experiences. The overall correlation ($r = .817$) further confirms that the comprehensive development of professional capabilities significantly enhances satisfaction levels, reflecting the integrative and practice-oriented design of the MAEd curriculum.

These findings align with Astin’s (1993) Input–Environment–Outcome (I–E–O) Model, which posits that enriched academic environments foster enhanced learning outcomes and satisfaction. Likewise, Kember and Leung (2005) emphasized that active and reflective learning experiences contribute to graduates’ professional growth and positive academic perceptions, while Tynjälä (2013) highlighted the role of experiential and workplace-integrated learning in developing practical expertise and professional identity.

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Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{03})—stating that there is no significant relationship between the extent of professional impact and the level of satisfaction—is rejected. The findings substantiate that higher professional impact corresponds to greater satisfaction, affirming the MAEd program’s sustained quality, relevance, and effectiveness in advancing professional excellence in graduate education.

4.0 Conclusion

The MAEd program demonstrates a very high level of professional impact among its graduates. Results revealed that graduates consistently rated their professional competencies—particularly in leadership, management, social interaction, communication, and research—as very high, signifying that the program effectively enhances their pedagogical, administrative, and scholarly capabilities in alignment with graduate education standards (Guskey, 2002; Kember & Leung, 2005).

Graduates reported a very high level of satisfaction with the MAEd program. Across all dimensions—faculty competence, quality of instruction, learning resources, support services, and student development activities—the ratings indicate that graduates perceive the academic environment as enriching, supportive, and conducive to continuous professional growth (Harvey & Green, 1993).

No significant differences were found in professional impact and satisfaction when grouped by profile variables. The Kruskal–Wallis test results showed that age, gender, specialization, agency affiliation, length of service, present position, and year graduated did not significantly influence perceptions of professional impact and satisfaction ($p > 0.05$). This demonstrates that the program provides equitable learning opportunities and consistently high-quality training across diverse demographic and professional contexts (Suh & Kim, 2022).

A strong and positive correlation exists between professional impact and satisfaction. The Spearman’s Rho coefficients ($r = .548 - .817$, $p < 0.01$) confirmed that as graduates’ perceived professional competencies improve, their satisfaction with the program also increases. This relationship underscores the effectiveness of MAEd instruction and mentoring in simultaneously fostering competence and fulfillment (Astin, 1993; Tynjälä, 2013).

The program exhibits sustained quality and relevance across academic years. Consistent results from cohorts 2019–2024 affirm that Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. maintains academic excellence and institutional commitment to graduate education, ensuring continuity in curriculum standards and instructional delivery.

Overall, the MAEd program of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. is proven to be impactful, inclusive, and transformative. Its outcomes reflect an educational framework that cultivates competent, ethical, and research-oriented professionals prepared to lead educational institutions and contribute to community development. Hence, the null hypotheses are accepted for group differences but rejected for the relationship test, validating the program’s enduring strength, equity, and scholarly impact in the field of advanced teacher education.

5.0 Contribution of the Authors

Both authors, Brenda A. Alvarez and Rowena R. Diaz, contributed equally to the conceptualization, data collection, analysis, and manuscript preparation of this study. Alvarez led the research design, data interpretation, and writing of the results and discussion, while Diaz coordinated data gathering, statistical validation, and review of literature integration. Both authors jointly reviewed and approved the final manuscript for submission.

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6.0 Funding Agency

This research was fully funded by Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc., through the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR). The institution provided administrative support, access to research participants, and logistical assistance throughout the study. No external funding was received from public or private agencies.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The study was conducted with strict adherence to research ethics as approved by the College Research Ethics Committee of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc. All procedures followed the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173) and the Ethical Standards for Educational Research of the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR). Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality and anonymity were ensured.

8.0 Acknowledgment

The researchers extend their deepest gratitude to their research adviser, Rowena R. Diaz, for the invaluable guidance, expertise, and encouragement that shaped the completion of this study. Appreciation is likewise given to the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR) of Christ the King College of Calbayog City, Inc., for the institutional support, and to the MAEd graduates who generously shared their time and insights. The authors also thank their families, mentors, and colleagues for their unwavering moral support and inspiration throughout the research process.

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